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RESEARCH OF THE LENGTH OF WOOL FIBERS, BODY TYPES, AND THE EXPRESSION OF COLORING IN LAMBS OF DIFFERENT COLORS

In the article, the length of wool fiber, types of constitution, and the expression of wool color of Karakol lambs of different colors were studied in the conditions of a breeding farm, while no reliable difference was observed between the groups. Only the silver sur lambs have slightly higher indicators, which indicates that they are in the process of adaptation to the conditions.

Keywords: *black, lamb, silver color, golden color, color, build, desert, skin, curly.*

The length of the wool fiber of Karakol lambs is an important feature in assessing the commercial properties of their skins. Different types and shapes of Karakol skin flowers have different lengths of wool fibers [1].

According to Yu.Yusupov (2010), the length of wool fibers can only be regulated by selection. A.Ombaev (2008), noting that this trait is a genetic trait, noted that it has significant variability depending on nutritional conditions.

S.Yusupov (2010), S.Bozorov (2015) note that the length of wool fiber at the time of birth of lambs is to a certain extent related to their body type, live weight and color. The results obtained in our experiment are presented in table 1 [2,3].

Table 1

Length of wool fibers of lambs of different colors, mm
(Data from H. Tursunov, 2007)

Colour variety	Number of lambs obtained	On a stump			On the back edge		
		M±m	g	S, %	M±m	G	S, %
Silver paint	106	10,24±0,13	1,13	15,7	11,73±0,12	1,2	14,3
Gold paint	60	10,41±0,17	1,17	11,9	12,12±0,13	1,4	12,4

As can be seen from the data in the table, the silver colored lambs had a shorter wool fiber length at the withers and 11.73 mm at the back edge, the wool fiber length was relatively golden. The lambs had a wool length of 10.41 mm at the withers and 12.12 mm at the back edge.

Body types of lambs of different colors

It is important to consider the constitutional types of Karakol sheep and lambs. The constitutional type of Karakol lambs is one of the main features, and this feature is an indicator of health, vitality, adaptability to extreme desert conditions and productivity of sheep. Karakol lambs are assessed by the level of development and constitution at birth and are divided into 3 groups.

Strong constitutional type of Karakol lambs - according to the rate of development of such lambs, the live weight is 4-4.5 kg, the skeleton is strong, normal, the body structure is proportional, the skin is thin, clean, the wool cover is silky, medium shine, the fineness of the curls is average, the wool cover of secondary parts of the body is average, the skin reserve, the fatness is from good to average.

Coarse type of constitution of Karakol lambs - these lambs are high-bodied, weigh 4-6 kg, have a coarse skeleton, a relatively short head, a wide, very rounded body, without legs, the body is wide, restrained, the skin is thick, mature or less clear, loose, the wool is predominantly coarse, the curls are enlarged, but can also be of medium size, secondary parts of the body are rarely covered with wool.

Thin type of constitution of Karakol lambs - lambs of this type are small, weigh up to 3.5 kg, have a compact skeleton or are elongated due to the facial part, narrow, have a straight or slightly concave profile, have smaller curls, sometimes medium, secondary parts of the body are covered with thick wool, sometimes somewhat more sparse.

Currently, in animal husbandry, including cattle breeding, the classification of P.Kuleshov and M.Ivanov is widely used, which is mainly divided into coarse, thin, loose and strong types of constitution.

S.Bozorov (2015) argues that the productivity of constitutional type animals is expressed depending on their reaction to the external environment and that yellow sheep are constitutionally weaker than black ones, therefore their feeding and care should be given special attention.

S.Bozorov (1998), S.Sattorov, M.Egamkulov, S.Bozorov (2001) established that mating sheep with a strong constitution allows obtaining 81% of offspring of this type.

S.Yusupov (2010), S.Bozorov (2015) and others paid great attention to the importance of constitutional types and noted the need to evaluate lambs according to this indicator during examination [2,3,4].

Table 2

Constitution types of lambs of different colors, %

Colour variety	Number of lambs	Delicate		Strong		Rude	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
Silver paint	106	14	13,2	75	70,8	17	16,0
Gold paint	60	7	11,7	42	70,0	11	18,3

As can be seen from the data in Table 2 above, silver-colored lambs have a relatively large number of thin-type lambs, which amounted to 13.2%. Among golden-brown-colored lambs, there were more lambs of the coarse type of constitution, which amounted to 18.3%. The output of lambs of the solid type of constitution was almost the same for silver and golden-yellow-colored lambs. There is no significant correlation between the color of the coat and the type of constitution.

Expression of sur color in lambs of different colors

The intensity of color in lambs is one of the main quality indicators, this feature is an indicator that is passed on from generation to generation, and this indicator also depends on the influence of the external environment, mainly pasture conditions. Strong expression of this indicator is an important and selective feature in determining the breeding value of lambs, as well as in assessing the market value of black skins, and in lambs left for breeding, this indicator must be given great attention.

In Karakol lambs, the brown color is formed as a result of uneven distribution of pigment along the length of the fiber. The pigment is abundant at the base of the fiber, spreads to it, giving it a dark color, and decreases at the tip, giving various light colors. The pronounced expression of this feature has an important and first-class selection value in determining the breed of lambs, assessing the market value of black sheepskins (Table 3).

As can be seen from the table, the expression of silver coloration in silver-colored lambs was very high and amounted to 37.7%. Lambs with unsatisfactory coloration were 10.0% more in golden-yellow colored lambs and 3.4% more than in silver-yellow colored lambs.

Table 3

Expression of sur color in lambs of different colors (%)

Colour variety	Number of lambs	Excellent		Good		not satisfied	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
Silver paint	106	40	37,7	59	55,7	7	6,6
Gold paint	60	20	33,3	34	56,7	6	10,0

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